

Modular programme for Education and Training

EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATOR

*M#4 Fundamental Movement Skills, Play and Motor Skill
Assessment*

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For further information on the EduPASS Project please follow the link:

Website: <https://edupass-project.eu/>

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Six Core Modules of EduPASS for Early Childhood Educators

The following are the proposed six core modules for Early Childhood Educators education and training programmes that were developed as part of the EduPASS Erasmus+ Project. The core modules should be seen as a flexible reference point which require contextual adaptation. Those individuals and/or organisations using the six core modules to develop learning opportunities for Early Childhood Educators should use the knowledge of their specific context to customise the modules to fit their needs, resources and objectives.

Each of the six EduPASS core modules proposed for ECE education and training programmes was developed building on the knowledge and insights, which can be found in the [European Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care \(ECEC\)](#). The ECEC describes the most important the proposal for key principles of a [Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care \(2014\)](#).

The respective module number and order in which the modules are presented in the table below do not indicate that modules must be introduced in this specific order, when implementing an Early Childhood Educator education and training programme. Rather the numbers simply serve as distinct denominators to help identify specific modules in the overall context of the EduPASS ECE education and training programme.

Core Module Overview

No	Module Title	Description
1	Daily Physical Activity and Play	<p>The module teaches the theoretical basis of the concept of holistic development of children, focusing on changes experienced by children aged 3 to 6 years.</p> <p>It emphasizes the importance of physical activity and play in children's overall development and well-being and highlights the benefits of physical activity during childhood, as well as the potential risks of inactivity on overall health. Additionally, recommendations for children's physical activity levels, strategies for implementation, and the development of skills for assessing the recommended daily physical activity level for children are provided.</p> <p>Finally, a theoretical background for developing intervention programs aimed at improving children's daily physical activity levels is presented. It includes practical workshops and the development of skills for designing and implementing programs to enhance children's daily physical activity levels.</p>

2	Principles of Educating Children	<p>This module aims to guarantee the comprehensive development of children through physical education. For this, different learning units, based mainly on the game, will be carried out such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • motor stories • music, dance and movement • energetic games • games with balls • activities that involve balance, development of laterality, coordination and body awareness • manipulative and construction games
3	Inclusive Teaching	<p>The module aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduce the theoretical foundations of the concept of inclusion. This includes the legal background (e.g., UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and national legislation), the requirements and goals of inclusion, and didactic models, principles, methods, and strategies for inclusive teaching. • provide opportunities to practically apply and reflect about the principles, methods, and resources of inclusive teaching using specific teaching/case scenarios.
4	Fundamental Movement Skills, Play and Motor Skill Assessment	<p>The module aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduce the theoretical basics of the concept of fundamental movement skills and play and their importance for children. This includes the structure of fundamental movement skills, their role in children’s development, and didactic principles and methods to promote fundamental movement skills and play. • provide guidance on the practical use of the principles, methods, and resources of teaching/promoting fundamental movement skills and play. • introduce both the theoretical knowledge and the practical skills to objectively measure fundamental movement skills of children using motor tests
5	Hands-on Teaching	<p>This module is designed to enhance the practical skills of Early Childhood Educators through direct participation in learning activities. Through a hands-on approach, participants will develop key skills to foster high-quality interactions with children and create an inclusive learning environment.</p> <p>During the module, Early Childhood Educators will engage in interactive exercises and receive immediate feedback, allowing them to directly apply the pedagogical techniques learned to their educational settings. Strategies for observation and documentation, group dynamics management, and conflict resolution will be addressed, all focused on adapting pedagogical practices to the individual and collective needs of children.</p>

6	Plan, Reflect and Learn	<p>The application of teaching skills, observation and effective decision making is essential to fulfil teaching PAMPS for early childhood and is a cross-cutting capability that should be developed in all ECEs at each stage of their development. The ECE plans, evaluates and reflects each practice and event seeking improvements. In addition, this personal evaluation and reflection underpin a process of ongoing learning and professional development. An important element of this process is the ECE's efforts to with other ECEs in the process.</p> <p>Reflection plays a vital role in early childhood settings. It provides continuous professional development, support, and feedback for all members involved and gives ECEs a safe space to discuss challenging experiences and related feelings. It lays the groundwork for ongoing professional development through consistent self-reflection, community support, and emotional awareness. It's critical that educators can manage the feelings that come with stress to support children's development, communicate effectively with co-workers and families, and find job satisfaction.</p> <p>Questioning what learning and development is taking place to make meaning of what has been observed is crucial for ECE. ECE students should be able to describe why the events are significant to the child and to describe why this experience was important for the child involved.</p>
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Core Module Structure

Core Module	Fundamental Movement Skills, Play and Motor Skill Assessment
Module Number	4
Core Module Aim	<p>The aim of the core module is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> to clarify the concept of fundamental movement skills and play and their importance for the motor and psycho-social development of children. to convey methods and strategies for promoting fundamental movement skills and play in practice. to convey knowledge and skills for assessing fundamental movement skills using motor tests.
Module Description	<p>The module consists of three courses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Course 4.1: This course teaches the theoretical basics of the concept of fundamental movement skills and play and their importance for children. This includes the structure of fundamental movement skills, their role in children's development, and didactic principles and methods to promote fundamental movement skills and play. Course 4.2: This course is focused on the practical use of the principles, methods, and resources of teaching/promoting fundamental movement skills and play. Course 4.3: This course teaches both the theoretical knowledge and the practical skills to objectively measure fundamental movement skills of children using motor tests.
Module Duration	30 hours
Facilities and Equipment	<p>Facilities: Seminar room and gym.</p> <p>Equipment: Usual equipment for teaching/promoting PAMPS with children.</p>
Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Course 4.1: Class-based lectures and presentations, work in pairs and small groups, if applicable independent/self-directed working. Course 4.2: Field-based sessions, peer teaching, specific teaching/task scenarios, work in small groups, independent/self-directed working. Course 4.3: Class-based lectures and presentations and field-based sessions, peer teaching, work in pairs and small groups.
Coaching Materials	Logbook / reflection book
Suggested Readings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Colvin A.V., Egner Markos, E.J., & Walker, P.J. (2022). Teaching fundamental motor skills (4^{ed} Ed.). Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics. Lubans, D.R., Morgan, P.J., Cliff, D.P., Barnett, L.M., & Okely, A.D. (2014). Fundamental movement skills in children and adolescents: review of associated health benefits. <i>Sports Medicine</i>, 40, 1019-1035. Bös, K. (Hrsg.) (2017). <i>Handbuch Motorische Tests</i> (3. Überarb. und erw. Auflage). Göttingen: Hogrefe.

Evaluation	EduPASS Evaluation Tool for Early Childhood Educator Programmes					
Module structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 courses)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Course 4.1: Fundamental Movement Skills and Play and their Importance for Children’s Development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 4 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 4 h Seminar / Workshop Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours ● Course 4.2: Promoting Fundamental Movement Skills and Play <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Seminar Teaching Units ○ 4 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours ● Course 4.3: Assessment of Fundamental Movement Skills and Play <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Seminar Teaching Units ○ 4 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours 					
Learning outcomes <i>for Early Childhood Educators</i>	<p>The module will enable the Early Childhood Educator in training to build the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values) which serve as a foundation when engaging with the children they teach:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="391 958 1396 1514"> <tr> <td data-bbox="391 958 890 1167"> Knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Children’s needs ● Child development ● Pedagogical knowledge </td> <td data-bbox="890 958 1396 1167"> Skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communication skills ● Promoting fun and enjoyment ● Organizational skills ● Teaching / pedagogical skills </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="391 1167 890 1514"> Attitudes: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they teach:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cooperation ● Motivation ● Enthusiasm </td> <td data-bbox="890 1167 1396 1514"> Values: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they teach:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fair play ● Respect ● Ethical practice </td> </tr> </table>		Knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Children’s needs ● Child development ● Pedagogical knowledge 	Skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communication skills ● Promoting fun and enjoyment ● Organizational skills ● Teaching / pedagogical skills 	Attitudes: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they teach:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cooperation ● Motivation ● Enthusiasm 	Values: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they teach:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fair play ● Respect ● Ethical practice
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Learning outcomes <i>for children/learners</i>	<p>The module will enable the Early Childhood Educator in training to support the children they teach to develop the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values):</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="391 1630 1396 2042"> <tr> <td data-bbox="391 1630 890 1921"> Knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Awareness about their interests and preferences ● Regarding basic motor development processes ● Activities in PAMPS ● Fundamentals of social interaction </td> <td data-bbox="890 1630 1396 1921"> Skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fun and enjoyment ● Communication skills ● Cooperation skills ● Motivation skills </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="391 1921 890 2042"> Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the</i> </td> <td data-bbox="890 1921 1396 2042"> Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following</i> </td> </tr> </table>		Knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Awareness about their interests and preferences ● Regarding basic motor development processes ● Activities in PAMPS ● Fundamentals of social interaction 	Skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fun and enjoyment ● Communication skills ● Cooperation skills ● Motivation skills 	Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the</i>	Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following</i>
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Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the</i>	Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following</i>					

	<p><i>following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respecting other children’s needs and interests • Fun and enjoyment • Empathy • Enthusiasm 	<p><i>values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Fair play • Cooperation • Empathy
<p>Module Outcomes <i>action oriented outcomes and results for educators</i></p> <p><i>(based on Quality Statements from EU Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care, 2014)</i></p>	<p>After successful completion, the Early Childhood Educator in training will be able to:</p> <p>Coaching Vision and Strategy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a suitable vision for the programme relevant to the participants (and in line with institutional priorities). • Make effective and informed decisions relating to the planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of mid- to long-term programmes (of practice and competition) based on (institutional and) participant needs. <p>Shape the Environment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to identify, reflect on and challenge prevailing beliefs, values and assumptions within the coaching environment to establish a suitable culture for PAMPS. <p>Building Positive Relationships:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to establish and maintain an ethical, effective, inclusive and empathetic relationship with children and other stakeholders (e.g., parents). • Understand how to appreciate physical, mental and cultural diversity in children and adapt PAMPS practice accordingly. <p>Coaching Practice:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to conduct (comprehensive) needs analyses for individual children (and/or teams) in order to design and deliver tailored coaching programmes, taking into account children needs and capabilities (in the context of wider programmes, curricula, policies and targets). • Understand how to select, design, and justify appropriate pedagogy, practice and communication methods to facilitate the short, medium and long-term learning needs of children. • Understand the core elements of multi skills or of their chosen sport(s) at the key stages of child development. • Know how to deliver a series of coaching sessions in the context of medium term and long term planned programmes of practice and competition using a wide range of appropriate learning modes for children and coaching behaviours. <p>Decision Making:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand how to conduct an informed analysis of own performance and of the performance of children towards ensuring continuous progress and improvement. • Understand how to make good in-action and post-action decisions to increase the chances of reaching short, mid and long term objectives. <p>Coaching Review and Reflection:</p>	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Know how to conduct an insightful analysis of coaching practice to make informed judgements relating to the efficacy of the learning environment established.
Connection to other Core Module	Module 1: Daily Physical Acitivity and Play

Course Structure

Course Title	Fundamental Movement Skills and Play and their Importance for Children’s Development		
Course Number	4.1		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>In this course, the theoretical basics of fundamental movement and fundamental play are taught and their importance for the psycho-social and motor development of children is highlighted. The Early Childhood Educator in training will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • understand the structure and development of fundamental movement skills and fundamental play. • understand the importance of fundamental movement skills and play for the healthy development of children. • get to know didactic principles and methods to promote fundamental movement skills and play effectively. <p>The main objective of this course is to introduce the Early Child-hood Educator in training with the concept of fundamental movement skills and play its practical implications.</p>		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L	4 h	Teaching Unit 1: Fundamental Movement Skills and Play
	S	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Principles, Methods, and Resources to promote Fundamental Movement Skills and Play
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Preparing a Teaching Activity
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundamental movement skill and play and children’s development 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to promote FMS and play in children? 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparing a teaching activity for course 4.2 	

Course Title	Principles, methods, and resources to promote fundamental movement skills and play		
Course Number	4.2		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>In this course, the principles, methods, and resources of promoting fundamental movement skills and play introduced in course 4.1 are deepened and practically applied and reflected using specific teaching/task scenarios. The Early Childhood Educator in training will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • deepen his/her knowledge on and practically use the didactic principles, methods, and resources of promoting fundamental movement skills and play. • understand how to prepare and implement teaching activities for promoting fundamental movement skills and play. <p>The objective of this course is to familiarize the Early Childhood Educator in training with the principles and methods of teaching fundamental movement skills and play.</p>		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Repetition of course 4.1
	S	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: Deepening and Interactive Discussion
	W	6 h	Teaching Unit 3: Preparing and Implementing Teaching Activities
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 4: Reflection and Evaluation
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repetition of course 4.1 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deepening and interactive discussion of the principles, methods • Resources to promote FMS and play. 	
	TU 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation and implementation of the teaching activities (peer teaching, pairs or small groups) 	
	TU 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflection and evaluation of the teaching activities 	

Course Title	Assessment of Fundamental Movement Skills and Play		
Course Number	4.3		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The course provides both the theoretical knowledge and the practical skills to objectively assess fundamental movement skills using motor tests. The Early Childhood Educator in training will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • learn why it is important to objectively measure fundamental movement skills and how this information can be used. • get to know various motor tests used to measure fundamental movement skills and play in childhood and how to prepare, implement and evaluate them. • learn how motor tests can be integrated into teaching activities without creating a testing situation for the children. <p>The course aims to enable the Early Childhood Educator in training to assess fundamental movement skills objectively and pedagogically appropriate.</p>		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / S	4 h	Teaching Unit 1: Motor Tests to Measure Fundamental Movement Skills and Play in Childhood
	W / PE	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Preparing, Implementing, and Analyzing Motor Tests
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Reflection and Evaluation
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examples of motor tests, quality criteria, pedagogical aspects • How to use motor tests in pedagogical settings? 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation and implementation of a motor test activities (peer teaching, pairs or small groups) 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guided reflection and evaluation of the motor test activity, feedback to the students, using of the data 	